

Models of Psychologist Activity

Adamova Ugiljon¹

¹ Senior teacher, Urgench state university

Abstract:

In this article, it is emphasized that a person should always strive to be peaceful, calm and certainly happy in life, to choose the right path and, if necessary, to rely on the advice of psychologists. The article talks about the counseling process, which is one of the models of the psychologist's activity and is considered the most important.

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The successes achieved in New Uzbekistan encourage the implementation of new reforms in society. One of the main directions of these reforms is spiritual-educational reforms, the main goal of which is to form the worldview of society members in the spirit of independence and to form and create the psychology of a person of a new era adapted to the conditions of New Uzbekistan. The basis of our state's youth policy is also aimed at forming a new worldview with a new attitude [1,12 b].

A whole generation of scientists, who are representatives of the science of psychology, searched for the laws of understanding the fundamental essence of man, his development and maturation in the system of relations between the individual and society. Hundreds of scholars of the East, such as Abu Nasr Farabi, Alisher Nawai, Ibn Sina, Al-Biruni, dedicated their masterpieces to unraveling the philosophical and social secrets of this interdependence. What is common to all views is that in order to understand a person and his essence, it is first necessary to know his place and position in this society.

Psychological counseling is considered a relatively new field in the professional activity of a psychologist, and in the development of science in our country, scientific research on psychology has recently emerged as an independent field of activity, along with traditional forms of practical work such as teaching psychology, psychological correction, and psychodiagnostics [4 ,77 b].

Undoubtedly, this activity requires special, deep knowledge and professional training from a specialist. It is impossible to simply organize this training, to replace it with the above-mentioned areas of knowledge and skills, but all these knowledge are very necessary for a psychologist-consultant.

Knowledge in the field of psychological counseling is mandatory not only for those who want to become practical psychologists, but also for social service workers and defectologists (specialists in the field of psychology).

Counseling as the main type of psychological practice has the following goals:

1. To help him in solving the problem that arose in the dispute immediately.
2. Assisting the client in solving problems that he can solve independently without the constant intervention of a psychologist, that is, in solving problems that usually do not require special professional psychological knowledge, only communication and life advice based on healthy content are needed. For example, choosing a convenient schedule for work and rest for the client, the correct distribution of time between different activities can be considered such issues.
3. Provision of temporary help in cases where a more or less permanent psychotherapeutic effect should be provided to the client for a long time, but due to one or another reason, it is not possible to do so in this situation. It can be used as a means of providing temporary operational support to the client, preventing the rapid development of negative processes, preventing the problem from getting worse. An example of such a problem can be when a client suddenly becomes depressed.
4. The client correctly understood his problem and was generally ready to solve it himself, but he doubted something, he was not fully confident that he was doing the right thing. In some cases, as a result of the psychologist-consultant communication, they receive professional and spiritual support, which increases their self-confidence.
5. Helping the client when there is no other option but to get advice. In such a case, the psychologist-expert, while giving psychological advice to the client, tries to explain that he needs a more serious and long-term psychocorrective or psychotherapeutic help.
6. Psychological counseling is not a substitute for other types of psychological assistance to the client, but not only a psychologist, but he himself is engaged in solving the problem together with them, additional training conducted as
7. The psychologist-consultant does not have a ready-made solution, because the situation is beyond his scope, and in cases where the client needs to be provided with very little and ineffective help, psychological counseling solves the following main tasks [6.247 b].
 - a) Clarify and understand the problem faced by the client.
 - b) To explain to the client about the nature of the problem, its seriousness, and to introduce the client to the problem.
 - c) The psychologist-consultant's study of the client's personality in order to determine whether the client can independently solve the problem that has arisen.
 - d) To clearly express advice and recommendations to the client on showing the best way to solve the client's problem.
 - e) Provide daily support to the client as additional practical advice when the client starts to decide on his options.
 - f) To teach the client how to prevent the occurrence of similar problems in the future, a psychoprophylactic task.

g) Psychologist-consultant to provide the client with simple, life-necessary psychological knowledge and skills that he can apply himself.

Types of psychological counseling

1. Next, we will highlight the so-called intimate-personal psychological counseling, most people often have a demand for this kind of counseling
2. Family counseling is the next most important type of psychological counseling in life. This can include advice on issues that arise in a person's own family.
3. The third type of counseling consists of psychological and pedagogical counseling. This can include raising and teaching children with the client, training for a job, and improving the pedagogical skills of adults, pedagogical leadership, children's and adult groups, and community management.
4. The fourth most common type of psychological-pedagogical counseling is practical counseling. In turn, it has as many types as there are types of human activities. We found it necessary to give the following points as practical advice for a person to be happy.

How to be happy?

Every person dreams and strives to live a happy life. The great French writer Jean-Jacques Rousseau said that there are 3 conditions to be happy. These are:

1. A good bank account, that is, a modest income.
2. A good cook, that is, a person who makes it possible to eat delicious food.
3. A good stomach, that is, good digestion of food in human internal organs.

In the conducted studies, it was confirmed that even before these conditions, a person should feel happy in order to be happy. That's why psychologists put forward the following idea: "If you want to be happy, keep yourself happy."

We advise you not to forget and follow these 7 ways to be happy.

1. Love your loved ones. Give a lot of time and attention to your loved ones. You can feel happy about it.
2. Devote most of your energy to a hobby, profession or activity that you love. If you love your job, work hard. If you don't like it, try to change it, it will be more effective for you and for society. We spend a lot of time at work, and this time should not become a pain for us.
3. Help other people. There is altruism in every person, that is, the need to provide selfless help to others. By helping others, firstly, you will increase your self-esteem, secondly, you will get rid of your physical and psychological tension, i.e. stress, and as a result, you will have a feeling of satisfaction and happiness in life.
4. Strive to be happy. Watch yourself, think about what positively or negatively affects your mood [7.77 b]. Pursue what pleases you, of course, if it is a desire for goodness.
5. Physical activity. It is known that any physical activity and movement gives real pleasure to a healthy person, the reason for this has not been thoroughly studied. Academician Pavlov called this sensation muscle training. During physical activity, unique natural substances are produced in the human brain, and these substances give a person pleasure. Therefore, physical activities give a person a sense of happiness. You can dance, engage in any type of sport, or perform any exercise or movement that you can. You can feel happiness even if you get up in the morning in the winter to clear the sidewalk from the snow, shovel the ground, wash the windows with painstaking effort.

6. Try to introduce innovations into your life. From childhood, we are taught to approach everything in an orderly manner. A regular schedule, stable interests, learning a job, vacationing only in one place and time every year are all good, but everyone likes novelty. Therefore, from time to time, get out of order - that is, create something new. For example: go to work in a different way than the regular way, that is, pursue a hobby or take a vacation at a different time.
7. If you sometimes feel oppressed and unhappy, depressed, this is a psychological pendulum, because if you are happy today, you should remember that the opposite may also happen. Also, don't forget that the more positive the situation, the more negative it can be.

Therefore, it is necessary to effectively use the necessary conditions for a person to consider himself happy. Relying on the practical advice given by a psychologist has a positive effect on a person's life and makes a person perfect.

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